

The importance of artificial intelligence in developing administrative systems for government institutions in Iraq

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Abstract

With the increasing population growth in Iraq, various government institutions are witnessing a clear increase in the number of reviewers who lose effort, time and money in order to complete their work in these institutions, which in turn negatively affects the employee who makes a double effort to provide service to reviewers. Here, it was necessary to provide appropriate solutions that suit everyone, and these solutions would relieve the employee and simplify procedures for reviewers.

One of the most prominent of these solutions is to benefit from the tremendous progress in the technological arena and its arrival at very advanced stages represented by artificial intelligence applications that are expected to provide very great services to humanity.

In this study, we relied on the analytical approach to analyze the data collected from 160 employees from various state institutions through the approved study tool, which is a questionnaire consisting of 8 paragraphs to measure the impact of artificial intelligence on employee performance and diagnose the most important problems facing better utilization of it. The study concluded with a set of recommendations to achieve maximum benefit from artificial intelligence applications in government institutions.

Keywords: *Government institution, artificial intelligence applications, employee, administrative system, smartphone.*

1. Introduction

Artificial intelligence is one of the pillars of computer science and specializes in developing systems that simulate the functions of the human mind, such as analysis and decision-making, by training artificial intelligence models on very large amounts of data and recognizing its patterns to reach the stage where they can make decisions and reach very accurate results [1].

The idea of artificial intelligence originated in the early fifties of the last century, specifically with the mathematician Alan Turing, who raised this idea with his famous question (Can a machine think?) He conducted several experiments to answer his question using the Turing test to measure the ability of a computer to simulate the human mind [2].

As for the sixties and seventies of the last century, progress in the idea of artificial intelligence was relatively slow, but in the last two decades of the last century the idea became clear and advanced a lot and brought about tangible development such as the emergence of neural network technology and rule-based artificial intelligence technology [3].

Artificial intelligence can be divided into two parts: the first is weak artificial intelligence, which performs specific tasks, and strong artificial intelligence, which performs very large and powerful tasks based on knowledge that simulates human knowledge [4].

Artificial intelligence can be used in various fields, including health, education, services, security, military, and others. Artificial intelligence can be used in various fields, including health, education, services, security, military, and others [5].

We can notice that the mechanisms of work and performance of tasks in various government institutions that depend on modern means are considered the main axis of decision-making for that institution [6]. These means have developed with the great development of technology and have become an important pillar of organizing strategic planning to achieve aims at all levels through the use of data analysis and deducing results instead of guesswork or intuition as artificial intelligence is used to analyze this information and link it to reach accurate results [7].

2. Related Work

One of the researchers confirmed in his study that artificial intelligence is capable of enhancing economic growth and doubling productivity, but on the condition that it does not affect the development of the workforce [8].

In another study, researchers proved that artificial intelligence is able to support employees professionally by providing personal advice, discovering new opportunities, and identifying potential challenges. Artificial intelligence can also provide training to develop employee knowledge management [9].

In another study, the researcher proved that artificial intelligence can be the cornerstone of developing sustainable and efficient construction and infrastructure sectors in a manner consistent with the goal of the technology [10].

In another study, the researcher confirmed that the use of artificial intelligence in decision-making contributes to adapting to environmental requirements more quickly and accurately [11].

Another researcher confirmed in his study that the use of artificial intelligence in managing wireless communications has a positive impact on the results, speed of response and its accuracy [12].

In another study, the researcher confirmed the success of using artificial intelligence in managing the green energy program, as artificial intelligence predicts solar radiation, which leads to positive results [13].

3. Methodology

The study was conducted on 160 employees from different government institutions as a small sample to find out the extent of the use of artificial intelligence applications in government institutions and the possibility of developing its role to take up a larger space in performing jobs by conducting a questionnaire based on 5 paragraphs [14]. The samples were distributed according to gender, type of institution, and years of employee experience. The questionnaire was analyzed using the Likert scale to reach the most accurate results. As shown in the following table and chart.

Type of organization	Years of employee experience		gender		total	percentage (%)
	Less than 5 years	More than 5 years	males	females		
Health institution	28	21	30	19	49	30.6
Educational institution	41	22	36	27	63	39.4
Service institution	20	28	22	26	48	30.0
Total	89	71	88	72	160	100.0

Table (1) study samples.

Chart (1) study samples.

The questionnaire consisted of 5 questions related to the possibility of applying artificial intelligence in institutions. After receiving the answers to the questionnaire, the results were analyzed using a five-point Likert scale, where 5 answers were suggested; (Very much, A lot, Average, Little, very little), as in the following table.

Degree)	Response
1-1.6	Very little
1.6-2.2	Little
2.2-2.8	Average
2.8-3.4	A lot
3.4-4	Very much

Table (2) Likert scale probabilities

The five paragraphs that we adopted in the questionnaire and analyzed using the Likert scale were focused questions to determine the importance of artificial intelligence applications in institutions and the period of their readiness to benefit from it in order to obtain accurate results through which we can diagnose the problem and find solutions, as shown in the following table.

Paragraph number	Paragraph
1	Does the institution use artificial intelligence applications to perform its tasks?
2	How ready is the institution to benefit from artificial intelligence applications?
3	How much does the employee need to deal with AI applications?
4	Does the employee have a clear idea about artificial intelligence?
5	Do you want to develop artificial intelligence applications specific to your institution to perform tasks?

Table (3) Questionnaire paragraphs

After distributing the questionnaire to the samples and receiving the answers, they were analyzed based on the Likert scale, as the questionnaire inputs were the independent variables, which were determined by the type of institution, the number of years of experience, and gender [15]. As for its outputs, they were the results of the questionnaire after processing it according to the rules of the Likert scale, which are considered non-independent variables.

4. Results

By relying on the Likert scale to analyze the questionnaire results and identify the areas of strength and weakness in the mechanisms for applying artificial intelligence in government institutions and how to develop it and achieve maximum benefit from it, we calculated the arithmetic mean and standard deviation of the sample answers, then determined the percentage of each paragraph and the sample direction as in the following table.

Paragraph number	Very little	little	Average	A lot	Very much	Arithmetic mean	Standard deviation	ratio	Sample direction	Paragraph sequence
5	0	15	16	34	95	4.31	0.99	86.1	Very much	1
3	6	18	27	41	68	3.92	1.18	78.4	Very much	2
4	3	7	110	24	16	3.27	0.77	65.4	A lot	3
2	3	75	17	45	20	3.03	1.15	60.5	A lot	4
1	28	96	22	12	2	2.15	0.84	43.0	Little	5

Table (4) Questionnaire results and standard deviation

5. Discussion

After analyzing the results based on the analysis rules of the Likert scale, we found that paragraph No. 5, which was (Do you want to develop artificial intelligence applications specific to your institution to perform tasks?), was the paragraph that had the highest arithmetic average with a percentage 86.1% which indicates the employees' desire to use artificial intelligence applications and benefit from its services.

As for paragraph 3, which was (How much does the employee need to deal with AI applications?) it came in second place, which confirms the employee's desire and need to deal with artificial intelligence applications, which reduces his effort and time.

As for paragraph (Does the employee have a clear idea about artificial intelligence?) which is paragraph 4, it came third to indicate that the employee began a real search for artificial intelligence to increase his knowledge of it, its characteristics and uses.

In the penultimate place came paragraph 2, which is (How ready is the institution to benefit from artificial intelligence applications?) to show the level of readiness of institutions to benefit from artificial intelligence applications. Despite all these components, the use of artificial intelligence by institutions came last, as explained in paragraph 1, which is (Does the institution use artificial intelligence applications to perform its tasks?).

6. Conclusions

Artificial intelligence applications are among the most widespread applications at the present time and the most used at the personal level or at the level of various institutions. They are the focus of the world and application developers and are considered a very important means of maintaining the security and economy of the country as well as its scientific progress, which reveals the need for our institutions to join the global bandwagon and benefit from artificial intelligence applications in the best way by preparing specialized teams to develop artificial intelligence applications that meet the needs of our institutions, shorten distances, and save time and effort. This was confirmed by the desire of the employees whose answers we used as a sample for this study. At the end of this study, we call for more studies and discussions on the application of artificial intelligence in government institutions and work to prepare an aware generation that realizes the importance and danger of artificial intelligence applications.

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